

Supporting Information

Acidic Hydrogen Evolution Electrocatalysis at High-Entropy Alloys Correlates with its Composition-Dependent Potential of Zero Charge

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Experimental Procedures

Chemicals

Perchloric acid (HClO₄) and potassium chloride (KCl) were purchased from Sigma-Aldrich. All chemicals were used as supplied. All solutions were prepared with Milli-Q deionized water. Single barrel quartz capillaries, 0.9 mm inner and 1.2 mm outer diameter and 10 cm length with filaments were purchased from Sutter instrument.

Preparation of electrodes

All elements of the high-entropy alloy materials library (HEA-ML) were simultaneously deposited on a 100 mm diameter single crystal (100) Si wafer with 1000 nm wet thermal SiO₂ as a barrier layer against substrate reactions by combinatorial magnetron sputtering (DCA Instruments, Turku Finland) using five metallic targets: Ag (purity 99.99%), Ir (purity 99.9%), Pd (purity 99.99%), Pt (purity 99.99%), and Ru (purity 99.95%). Each target was oriented at an angle of 45° to the fixed sample located at the confocal point, giving a target-to-substrate distance of 18.5 cm. The five cathodes are equally spaced in a circle (72° apart), with this geometry resulting in nearly linear thickness gradients from each. The deposition process started from a base vacuum of 2×10^{-6} Pa at 25° C and was done without additional intentional heating. All targets were precleaned immediately before the film was deposited against individual closed shutters. Depositions were done in Ar (99.9999%) at a pressure regulated to 0.67 Pa. The power applied to each target was adjusted to yield the desired alloy composition at the substrate center, and the total deposition rate at that point was 0.3 nm/s. The polycrystalline Pt thin-film electrode was prepared using the same method for the HEA-ML fabrication with the Pt target which was not tilted. 20 nm Ti and 40 nm Pt were deposited on the Si wafer in sequence. The polycrystalline Au thin-film electrode was prepared using (100) Si wafer (Wacker) coated sequentially with Ti and Au by vapor deposition in a metal vaporization setup (Leybold, Germany). The elemental composition of the prepared HEA-ML was determined by energy-dispersive X-ray analysis (EDX) with an acceleration voltage of 20 kV using a scanning electron microscope (SEM, JEOL 5800) and a silicon-drift detector (INCA Xact, Oxford Instruments).

X-ray diffraction (XRD) analysis of electrodes

To analyze the crystal structure of the Pt, Au, and the HEA-ML in dependence of its chemical composition, room temperature XRD was carried out at selected areas of the ML using a Bruker D8 Discover X-Ray diffractometer in Bragg-Brentano geometry. The system is equipped with a 2D detector (VANTEC-500) and an Incoatec I μ S Cu high-brilliance microfocuss X-ray source with $\lambda=0.15418$ nm Cu K α radiation. The tube was operated at 1 mA tube current and 50 kV acceleration voltage, generating a tube power of 50 W. A collimator with a focus spot size of 1 mm \times 1 mm was used, resulting in a 1 mm² measurement area on the sample. Each measurement area was measured in coupled 2 θ - θ configuration. In four consecutive steps, frames were taken at the 2 θ / θ positions 20°/10°, 40°/20°, 60°/30° and 80°/40° with a measurement time of 60 s respectively. Hereby, the angle of the approached position depicts the center position of the detector. One frame collects the diffraction data in an angular 2 θ range of approximately $\pm 20^\circ$ around the center point, i.e. from 20° to 60° for 40° 2 θ . All frames were subsequently merged into one elongated frame and integrated with a wedge cursor in the 2 θ range from 8° to 96°, using the software DIFFRAC.SUITE EVA. For the visualization of the diffraction pattern, only an angular range from 20° to 95° 2 θ was displayed.

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Scanning electrochemical cell microscopy (SECCM): Tip preparation

After carefully cleaning a single barrel quartz capillary with wipes soaked in isopropanol, it was placed in a laser puller (Sutter instrument). It was pulled with the puller parameters of HEAT 600, FIL 4, VEL 40, DEL 130, PUL 104-120. The diameter of the tip was measured by SEM (FEI Quanta 3D). Only tips having diameters of about 1 μm were used for further SECCM experiments. After filling the capillary with electrolyte 10 mM HClO_4 solution, the wider end of the single barrel SECCM tip was attached to an Eppendorf tip, of which the ending was slightly cut (Figure S1b). A Ag/AgCl (3 M KCl) reference electrode was used, and the potential of the reference electrode was calibrated before and after electrochemical experiments.

SECCM: Instrumental set-up

All electrochemical experiments were conducted using a home-built SECCM.^[1] The SECCM was controlled by FPGA card (PCIe-7852R) and a LabVIEW (National Instruments) software that was modified based on the Warwick Electrochemical Scanning Probe Microscopy (WEC-SPM) toolbox. SECCM was installed on a vibration-damping table (RS 2000, Newport) with four S-2000 stabilizer legs (Newport). A single barrel SECCM tip and an electrode were mounted on a pipette holder and a sample holder, respectively. The pipette holder was kept stationary while the sample holder was coarsely moved by x,y,z-stepper motors (Owis) with a LStep PCIe (Lang) controller, and was finely controlled by a x,y,z-piezo cube (P-611.3S nanocube, Physik Instrumente) with an analog amplifier (E-664, Physik Instrumente). First, using the stepper motors, an optical camera (DMK 21AU04, The Imaging Source) and a cold light source (KL1500 LCD, Schott), the SECCM tip was carefully placed about 20-50 μm above an interested region of an electrode surface. Then, the tip was approached to the surface by movement of the z-piezo, and the lateral position of the tip during scan-hopping experiments was controlled by the x,y-piezoes. The electrochemical cell was a 2-electrode system, with the part of the electrode surface contacting the droplet as working electrode, and the Ag/AgCl (3 M KCl) reference electrode/counter electrode inserted into the Eppendorf tip from above. The current flowing through the reference electrode was measured using a variable gain transimpedance amplifier (DLPCA-200, FEMTO Messtechnik) and a variable gain voltage amplifier (DLPVA-100-B-S, FEMTO Messtechnik). All electrochemical experiments were conducted under Ar atmosphere to avoid any interference caused by O_2 .

Potential of zero charge (PZC) determination

The SECCM tip was approached to the electrode surface with a z-velocity of 0.5 $\mu\text{m}/\text{s}$ until the current was higher than the positive threshold or lower than the negative threshold, signaling that the droplet of the tip touched the electrode surface. The positive and negative thresholds were usually set to about 0.2 pA higher and lower than the background noise, respectively. The potential of zero charge measurement method consists of an initial approach of the tip to the sample surface, surface-cleaning cyclic voltammetry (CV), and the PZC measurement protocol (Figure 1). CVs were performed for at least 4 cycles with a potential range including the hydrogen underpotential adsorption region and the metal oxide formation region with a scan rate of 1 V/s. During the PZC measurement protocol, the tip was repetitively approached to the same position of the surface at a series of varying sample potentials. The current was measured for 2 s after each approach, followed by stepping the potential to a potential in the electrical double layer (EDL) region. This is for conditioning the electrode surface and make it free of hydrogen and oxygen adsorption before the next approach of the tip. Then, the tip was retracted, the working electrode potential was changed to the next approach potential, and the tip was approached again to the same location on electrode surface. The initial decay of the current upon contact of the SECCM tip droplet with the sample surface was fitted to the charging current equation of the series RC circuit (Equation 1). Then, the current was integrated until the time constant calculated from the fit result, which yields the amount of the EDL charge. Finally, the PZC was evaluated by taking the x-intercept of the linear fit of EDL charge vs approach potential. The first approach data was excluded during analyses because it reflects the charging of the arbitrary surface probably having adsorption of hydrogen or oxygen.

Hydrogen evolution reaction (HER) activity measurement

A SECCM tip with a diameter of $\sim 3 \mu\text{m}$ was utilized to obtain HER CVs of bare Pt and the selected Pt-Pd-Ru-Ir-Ag measurement areas of the HEA-ML in 10 mM HClO_4 under Ar atmosphere with a scan hopping mode of 4 X 4. The reference electrode was Ag/AgCl (3 M KCl), and the potential values were converted to the RHE scale ($E_{\text{RHE}} = E_{\text{substrate}} + E_{\text{Ag}/\text{AgCl}} + 0.059 \text{ pH}$). Here, $E_{\text{Ag}/\text{AgCl}}$ is 0.210 V, and pH of 10 mM HClO_4 is 2. CV cleaning cycles within the potential window from -0.6 V to 1.4 V vs Ag/AgCl (3 M KCl) were recorded at each measurement area before the HER activity measurements. Since the same SECCM tip was utilized for all the HER experiments, the surface area was calculated from the SECCM tip area.

Finite element simulations of the HER voltammogram

The mechanism of the PZC-dependent HER voltammograms at the SECCM was investigated by the finite element simulation using COMSOL Multiphysics 5.6 software. The HER voltammogram was solved with a time-dependent study. The stationary studies were preceded to obtain the initial conditions for the time-dependent studies. The geometry of the SECCM tip and the protruding droplet touching the electrode surface was modeled in 2D axisymmetric structure as depicted in Figure S17a. There was the inner Helmholtz plane (IHP) with a thickness of 0.4 nm right next to the electrode surface, where no ion transport was assumed.^[2] The height of the simulated electrolyte was ca. 500 μm , which is much longer than the diffusion layer thickness ($\sqrt{Dt} \approx 273 \mu\text{m}$). The simulated voltammetry at the geometry with elongated tip height did not show notable changes. Meshes are constituted of narrow mapped quadrangular discretization at the droplet and free triangular discretization at the pipette body. The smallest mesh size near the IHP of the EDL is less than 1 nm. The mesh size gradually increased as it was close to the bulk reservoir.

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The transport of H^+ and ClO_4^- in the electrolyte was solved using the Nernst-Planck-Poisson equations. In this physics, the Poisson equation (Equation S1) calculates the electric potential of the solution phase while the Nernst-Planck equation (Equation S2) describes the diffusional and migrational flux of chemical species in the solution.

(1) *Electrostatics: Poisson equation*

$$\nabla^2 \phi = -\frac{\sum z_i C_i F}{\varepsilon \varepsilon_0} \quad (S1)$$

Here, ϕ is the electric potential, z_i and C_i is respectively the charge and the concentration of the species i . F is the Faraday's constant, ε_0 is the vacuum permittivity, and ε is the relative dielectric constant. ε of the water was set to be 78, while that in the IHP was 2.^[3] The ground potential ($\phi = 0$) was applied to the bulk reservoir domain. The electric potential of the electrode surface was the difference between the electrode potential and the PZC.

(2) *Transport of diluted species: The Nernst-Planck equation*

$$\frac{\partial C_i}{\partial t} = -D_i \nabla C_i - \frac{z_i F}{RT} D_i C_i \nabla \phi \quad (S2)$$

Here, D_i is the diffusion coefficient of the species i , R is the gas constant, and T is the temperature. The concentration of the species at the bulk reservoir domain was fixed as their bulk concentrations. H^+ was consumed in the electrode surface because of the HER. The HER kinetics was represented by the Butler-Volmer kinetics model (Equation S3).^[2] Hydrogen oxidation reaction (HOR) was not considered because the HOR current was not observed in the experiment because of the Ar atmosphere and fast diffusing out of the produced H_2 through the droplet-air interface.

$$i = -i_{ref} \frac{C_{H^+}}{C_{H^+,ref}} \exp\left(-\frac{\alpha F}{RT} (E_{RHE} - E_{RHE,ref})\right) \quad (S3)$$

The reference state (3 mA/cm² at -0.2 V vs SHE) was set to have the similar scale to the experimental HER current density on a flat Pt electrode.^[4] The inward H^+ flux at the outer Helmholtz plane (OHP) was i/F . The current density was calculated by dividing the current by the area of the SECCM tip end, 7.0686 μm^2 . This considers the actual experimental situation where the contact area of the droplet to the electrode surface is not able to be measured.

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Results

1. General Information

Figure S1. (a) Typical SEM image of the glass microcapillary opening used as the SECCM tip with a diameter of about 1.1 μm. (b) The schematic illustration of the electrochemical cell used in the SECCM. A SECCM tip is fixed to the tip holder, and the electrode is put in the Petri dish set on the piezo. A constant flow of Ar is introduced using the tube connected to the Petri dish during the SECCM measurements, and the SECCM tip is placed in a hole with a diameter of several centimeters in the lid of the Petri dish. The bigger end of the SECCM tip was elongated with an Eppendorf pipette tip in order to put the Ag/AgCl (3 M KCl) reference electrode into the electrolyte.

Figure S2. Cyclic voltammograms in 10 mM HClO₄ at IrHEA (#8 of the Pt-Pd-Ir-Ru-Ag HEA) with Ar flow (blue) and without Ar flow (orange).

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Figure S3. Exponential fitting results of the initial current upon the contact at the approach potentials of (a) 0.6 V, (b) 0.5 V, (c) 0.4 V, (d) 0.3 V, and (e) 0.2 V vs Ag/AgCl (3 M KCl) to Equation (1).

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2. Material Characterization of the Sputtered Film-type Pt and Au Electrodes

Figure S4. Figure S5. (a) XRD 2D detector image and (b) corresponding XRD diffraction pattern obtained from the sputtered Pt film electrode. The XRD result show that the Pt film exhibits fcc phase (ICSD-243678).

Figure S6. (a) XRD 2D detector image and (b) corresponding XRD diffraction pattern obtained from the sputtered Au film electrode. The XRD result show that the Au film is strongly textured with mostly (111) and (222) facets (ICSD-64701).

SUPPORTING INFORMATION

3. Material Characterization of Pt-Pd-Ru-Ir-Ag HEA material library (HEA-ML)

Figure S7. Pie chart diagram indicating the relative elemental compositions at each of measurement area (MA) of the Pt-Pd-Ru-Ir-Ag HEA-ML.

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Table S1. Atomic % of each element and the estimated WF at eight locations in Pt-Pd-Ir-Ru-Ag HEA-ML where SECCM experiments were carried out.

MA name	Pt %	Pd %	Ir %	Ru %	Ag %	Estimated WF (eV)
#1	31.2	43.3	9.8	14.2	1.4	5.24
#2 (PtHEA)	32.3	45.2	9.0	12.5	9.7	5.25
#3	26.5	44.6	11.7	16.1	1.1	5.21
#4 (RuHEA)	18	38.4	18.0	24.3	1.3	5.14
#5	19.6	45.6	16.1	17.6	1.1	5.17
#6 (PdHEA)	17.8	62.1	11.3	8.0	0.8	5.19
#7	13.4	33.6	23.8	27.9	1.4	5.11
#8 (IrHEA)	12.2	39.9	26.2	21.0	0.9	5.13

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Figure S8. X-ray diffraction (XRD) patterns of the eight MAs (MA #1 – #8) and the reference XRD peaks of the PdPt fcc lattice.^[5]

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4. PZC Measurements of the Pt-Pd-Ru-Ir-Ag HEA-ML

Figure S9. Typical surface-cleaning CVs of (a) RuHEA, (b) IrHEA, (c) PdHEA, and (d) PtHEA with a scan rate of 1 V/s in 10 mM HClO₄ under Ar atmosphere.

Figure S10. Histograms of PZC at (a) RuHEA, (b) IrHEA, (c) PdHEA, and (d) PtHEA in 10 mM HClO₄ after surface-cleaning CV. The diameters of the SECCM tips used are (a–c) 1.0 μ m, and (d) 1.85 μ m. See Table S2 for the average and standard deviation of each PZC distribution.

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Figure S11. Histograms of PZC at (a) RuHEA, (b) IrHEA, (c) PdHEA, and (d) PtHEA in 10 mM HClO₄ without surface-cleaning CV. The diameters of the SECCM tips used are (a) 920 nm, (b) 1.1 μ m, (c) 795 nm, and (d) 980 nm. See Table S2 for the average and standard deviation of each PZC distribution.

Figure S12. (a) Primary element effects on PZC of the Pt-Pd-Ru-Ir-Ag. PZC of four locations are investigated after surface-cleaning CV at RuHEA, IrHEA, PdHEA and PtHEA in 10 mM HClO₄. PtHEA, PdHEA, RuHEA, and IrHEA respectively have the nearly highest atomic % of Pt, Pd, Ru, and Ir among the whole HEA-ML (see Table S1). (b) The PZC of the HEA-ML, which did not undergo surface-cleaning, showed little difference according to element content.

Table S2. Summary of the PZC distributions of in RuHEA, IrHEA, PdHEA, and PtHEA before and after surface-cleaning CV, related to Figure S9–10.

	Without surface-cleaning CV		After surface-cleaning CV	
	PZC	The number of data	PZC	The number of data
RuHEA	0.29 \pm 0.02 V	88	0.23 \pm 0.01 V	38
IrHEA	0.29 \pm 0.02 V	84	0.24 \pm 0.02 V	59
PdHEA	0.30 \pm 0.02 V	64	0.30 \pm 0.01 V	83
PtHEA	0.33 \pm 0.09 V	96	0.39 \pm 0.03 V	86

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Figure S13. Typical surface-cleaning CVs of the four locations of Pt-Pd-Ru-Ir-Ag, (a) #1, (b) #3, (c) #5, and (d) #7, with a scan rate of 1 V/s in 10 mM HClO₄ under Ar atmosphere.

Figure S14. Histograms of PZC at the four locations of Pt-Pd-Ru-Ir-Ag, (a) #1, (b) #3, (c) #5, and (d) #7, in 10 mM HClO₄. The diameters of the SECCM tips used are (a, b, d) 1 μ m and (c) 660 nm. Table S3 summarizes the average and standard deviation of each PZC distribution.

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Table S3. Summary of the PZC distributions of the four locations of Pt-Pd-Ru-Ir-Ag, (a) #1, (b) #3, (c) #5, and (d) #7, after surface-cleaning CV, related to Figure S13.

	PZC	The number of data
#1	0.35 ± 0.04 V	79
#3	0.32 ± 0.02 V	66
#5	0.28 ± 0.02 V	73
#7	0.23 ± 0.02 V	62

5. Hydrogen Evolution Reaction at the Pt-Pd-Ru-Ir-Ag HEA-ML

Figure S15. HER CVs in 10 mM HClO₄ under Ar atmosphere at the Pt-Pd-Ru-Ir-Ag with a scan rate of 0.1 V/s measured by SECCM. The straight lines show the average responses, and the green-coloured patches represent their standard deviations from 16 independent scan-hopping experiments. Arrows in (a) represent the direction of the scan.

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Figure S16. The relationship between HER current density and PZC at bare Pt and the Pt-Pd-Ru-Ir-Ag depending on the overpotential of (a) -50 mV, (b) -150 mV, and (c) -200 mV vs RHE. HER current values are taken from the forward scan of Figure 5a–b and Figure S14. Error bars represent the standard deviations of the averaging.

Figure S17. The relationship between the HER current density and PZC at bare Pt and the Pt-Pd-Ru-Ir-Ag depending on the overpotential of (a) -50 mV, (b) -100 mV, (c) -150 mV, and (d) -200 mV vs RHE. HER current values are taken from the backward scan of Figure 5a–b and Figure S14. Error bars represent the standard deviations of the averaging.

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6. COMSOL Simulation

a) Simulation geometry

b) Mesh

c) Physics: Electrostatics

d) Physics: Transport of diluted species

Figure S18. (a) The 2D axisymmetric geometry of the model consists of the pipette body and the protruding droplet. The length of the bulk reservoir, the height of the geometry, and the radius of the wetted electrode area are $60\ \mu\text{m}$, $500.1\ \mu\text{m}$, and $1\ \mu\text{m}$, respectively. (b) The mesh structure of the model. The pipette body was constituted of free triangular segments with extra fine element size, and the droplet was constituted of the mapped quadrangular segments with a minimum element size of $\sim 1\ \text{nm}$. (c-d) Summary of the applied physics in the model.

Table S4. The parameter values used in the numerical simulation.

Name	Value	Reference
Diffusion coefficient of H^+	$9.31 \times 10^{-9}\ \text{m}^2/\text{s}$	[6]
Diffusion coefficient of ClO_4^-	$1.79 \times 10^{-9}\ \text{m}^2/\text{s}$	[7]
Bulk concentration of HClO_4	10 mM	
pH of the electrolyte	2	
Relative dielectric constant of water at IHP	2	[3]
Relative bulk dielectric constant of water	78	[8]
Charge transfer coefficient of the Butler-Volmer kinetics	0.5	
Temperature	298 K	

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Figure S19. (a) Simulated HER voltammogram at the electrode PZC of 0.25 V and 0.45 V. To understand the peak shaped sigmoidal voltammogram, the concentration profiles of H^+ and ClO_4^- are investigated during the forward scan of the potential (E): -0.15 V, -0.172 V (peak potential of the CV on the electrode PZC 0.45 V), and -0.2 V. These points are designated as black dots in (a). (b-g) H^+ and ClO_4^- concentration profile and the magnified H^+ concentration profile at the electrode PZC of 0.45 V (b, e) at -0.15 V, (c, f) at -0.172 V, and (d, g) at -0.2 V. At the peak potential, -0.172 V, H^+ begins to deplete at the electrode surface. (h-m) H^+ and ClO_4^- concentration profile and the magnified H^+ concentration profile at the electrode with a PZC of 0.25 V (h, k) at -0.15 V, (i, l) at -0.172 V, and (j, m) at -0.2 V. Unlike the case of the PZC 0.45 V, the local concentration of H^+ did not reach zero at -0.172 V. It becomes depleted at the electrode surface when $E <$ peak potential. The sharp increase in H^+ concentration and decrease in ClO_4^- concentration in the vicinity of the electrode surface are to compensate for the negative surface charge of the electrode.

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PZC = 0.45 V

PZC = 0.25 V

Figure S20. The potential (E) dependent profile of the H^+ concentration and H^+ flux near the electrode surface up to about $6.5 \mu\text{m}$ height along the pipette when the electrode PZC is (a–c) 0.45 V and (d–f) 0.25 V . The size of the arrowhead is proportional to the flux magnitude. (a), (d), and (e) are before E reaches their peak potential, and (b), (c), and (f) are after E reaches their peak potential. (Peak potentials of the PZC 0.45 V case and the PZC of 0.25 V case are -0.172 V and -0.195 V , respectively.) (a), (d), and (e) feature the incomplete depletion of H^+ on the electrode surface and the spherical flux of H^+ near the electrode. In (b), (c), and (f), H^+ is fully consumed at the droplet, and the transport of H^+ along the pipette body determines the supply of H^+ to the electrode surface.

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Figure S21. Simulated HER voltammogram without considering migrational flux of species in the electrolyte.

Figure S22. (a–b) Electric potential and electric field profile near the electrode surface at -0.1 V vs RHE with the electrode PZC of 0.25 V and 0.45 V. (c) H⁺ concentration at the outer Helmholtz plane (OHP) across the electrode PZC at -0.1 V vs RHE.

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Author Contributions

M. Kim, W. Schuhmann and T. D. Chung conceived the project. M. Kim and E. B. Tetteh designed the experiments and carried out electrochemical experiments. M. Kim performed the COMSOL simulation. A. Savan and B. Xiao synthesized and characterized the HEA-ML, O. A. Krysiak determined the catalytic activity of the HEA-ML by scanning droplet cell. T. H. Piotrowiak conducted XRD measurements. A. Andronescu, M. Kim, E. B. Tetteh and W. Schuhmann wrote the manuscript with input from all authors. W. Schuhmann, C. Andronescu, T. D. Chung, and A. Ludwig supervised the study.

Appendix: Representative EDX Spectrums of the HEA-ML

Figure S22–S29 are the individual EDX spectrums for the eight measurement areas (MAs) for which PZC were measured as representatives for the overall EDX spectrums of the Pt-Pd-Ir-Ru-Ag HEA-ML. The Si and Ti signals originate from the wafer and adhesion layer, respectively.

Figure S23. EDX spectrum of MA #1.

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Figure S24. EDX spectrum of MA #2.

Figure S25. EDX spectrum of MA #3.

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Figure S26. EDX spectrum of MA #4.

Figure S27. EDX spectrum of MA #5.

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Figure S28. EDX spectrum of MA #6.

Figure S29. EDX spectrum of MA #7.

